

THE POTENTIAL CONTRIBUTION
OF OPTIMUM FREQUENCY ASSIGNMENT
TO EFFICIENT USE OF THE SPECTRUM

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ABSTRACT

It has been more than 15 years since it was realized that graph theory provides mathematical methods for optimum assignment of specific frequencies to radio system requirements. In this context, an "optimum assignment" is the set of frequencies for individual systems that uses the smallest total bandwidth to satisfy a given set of requirements under a given set of constraints. Although computer programs for optimum frequency assignment are not in general use for frequency selection, they have been used in several cases, and they offer the opportunity for enhanced efficiency of spectrum utilization in the twenty-first century.

This paper reviews the development of optimum frequency assignment programs, presents the evidence that they will improve efficiency of service band use, and suggests ways that the spectrum management community can capitalize on these opportunities.

INTRODUCTION

Apparently, Zoellner [1] was the first to realize that the optimum assignment of channels to radio systems is mathematically equivalent to the graph coloring problem of graph theory. He and Beall correctly described this discovery as "A breakthrough in spectrum conserving frequency assignment technology [2]." Hale [3] reviewed the history of these developments and provided a solid mathematical basis for applications to services with varying equipment bandwidths and with different inter-service and intra-service frequency-distance separation rules. Since then, the program developed by Hale [4] has been used for a number of analyses of spectrum-conserving strategies [5-8].

The program has also been used for some practical problems. The first session of the World Administrative Radio Conference (WARC) for High Frequency Broadcasting directed the International Frequency Registration Board (IFRB) to develop a computer-based methodology for assigning frequencies for international shortwave broadcasting [9]. The United States sent copies of Hale's program to the IFRB, who modified it and incorporated it into their planning system [10].

The Federal Communications Commission (FCC) and NTIA have used the program to analyze the tradeoffs involved in assigning additional bandwidth to existing television stations for the purpose of broadcasting high-definition television signals [11, 12]. An example of this analysis will be described later in this paper, after the principles of the computer program have been described.

FREQUENCY ASSIGNMENT PROGRAM

Individual users of the radio spectrum want to choose frequencies that will minimize interference to their communications system. On the other hand, the user community, in the person of the spectrum manager, wants to provide frequencies to everyone who wants one. These two desires oppose each other -- the more radio systems that are operating within a band, the greater is the probability of interference. The usual resolution of this conflict is to define an acceptable signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) or required protection ratio, and then to assign frequencies to as many users as possible without violating the interference condition. The frequency assignment computer program provides a (near) optimum selection of frequencies for this solution.

The input to the computer program is a list of the stations to be assigned and their locations, a list of stations already assigned and their locations, and a statement of the frequency assignment constraints between every pair of stations. The frequency assignment constraints are statements of how far apart in frequency the two stations must be. The constraints can be stated as frequency-distance (F-D) separation rules, for example, "Co-channel stations must be at least 75 miles apart; adjacent-channel stations must be at least 20 miles apart; ...". Alternatively, the constraints can be computed off-line based on detailed system characteristics and required SNR and supplied as input in a compatibility matrix. For practical applications, the total bandwidth available (the service bandwidth) is specified.

The graph-theoretical algorithms implemented in the program are described by Hale [4]. In general, the program assigns frequencies first to the most difficult stations (those with the most mutual incompatibilities with other stations). It tries to pack stations as close together in frequency as possible.

The output of the computer program is a list of the frequencies assigned to all stations that could be assigned under the constraints, and (in service bandwidth limited cases) a list of stations that could not be assigned because of the constraints and assignments to other stations. The program also provides summaries of these lists, and shows the distribution of channel loading.

EXAMPLE APPLICATIONS AND PRINCIPLES

The assignment program has been used to simulate a number of frequency assignment strategies for a variety of scenarios, a process pioneered by Zoellner [1]. The general procedure for such studies will now be described. A specified number of random station locations are generated in a square area of specified size. A set of frequency distance rules are defined, and the program produces an optimum table of frequency assignments. The significant result (such as total bandwidth required, or number of stations not assigned) is recorded, and another set of random locations is generated. When enough sets of locations have been analyzed to produce a robust average result, one of the input parameters is changed, and the process is repeated. The final result is a picture of how spectrum use is affected by the scenario parameters.

Two studies show the benefits of using the computer program to make assignments. In one study, the total bandwidth needed to assign all requirements using the program

was compared with the total bandwidth needed if each requirement is assigned the smallest available frequency as its location is randomly generated. (The "smallest available frequency" is the one nearest the bottom of the band that is compatible with already-assigned stations according to the prevailing frequency-distance separation rules.) Notice that this "bottom-packing" assignment method is already more spectrum-conservative than many prevailing frequency selection methods. The average spectrum saved by the optimum methods varied from 12 % for cases with only a co-channel separation distance rule to over 30 % for the complex set of frequency-distance separation rules called the "UHF taboos" (to be described later).

In many cases, the user applies for a particular frequency, without seeking the advice of the spectrum-assigning authority. The frequency is often chosen because it will minimize the chance of interference because it is unused except possibly very far away from the applicant's geographic location. To compare optimum assignment methods with this tendency to choose isolated frequencies, we implemented a "least-used frequency" algorithm. In this algorithm, a requirement is assigned the frequency that is least used by previous assignments of all those that satisfy the frequency-distance separation rules. Scenarios using this algorithm must have a limited bandwidth available because, otherwise, the method would assign a unique channel to all requirements.

In the second study of the benefits of optimum frequency selection, 200 stations were randomly located in a square with 300-mi sides. The co-channel separation distance was 75 mi, and there were no other F-D rules. The service band contained 25 channels. Table 1 shows the average results for ten different cases for this scenario. The first column of the table contains the assignment strategy, the second column shows the average number of channels needed to assign all requirements (if the total was no more than 25), and the third column shows the average number of requirements that could not be assigned channels without violating the frequency-distance separation rule.

Table 1. Comparison of channels used by different selection strategies for the scenario described in text.

Method	channels	denied
Best	21.0	0.0
First avail	24.2	1.2
Least used	25.0	4.8

The method called "best" in Table 1 is the usual output from the optimum frequency assignment program. The method called "first avail" is the "bottom-packing" method, in which requirements are assigned one-at-a-time as they are received to the smallest channel that satisfies the F-D rules. Notice that the "best" method assigned the 200 requirements in 21 channels. The "first available" method assigned all requirements in 25 or fewer channels for some cases, and for some other cases it could not assign all requirements within the rules, so some requirements were denied assignments. This method used an average of 24.2 channels, and denied an average of 1.2 of the requirements. The "least-used" method (modeling current practice in many bands) used all 25 channels for every case, and denied frequencies to almost 5 applicants on the average. These applicants were denied because earlier applicants were assigned channels so inefficiently that there were none left that satisfied the F-D rules for the later applicants.

The main reason that the best method in Table 1 is better than the first-available method is that the requirements are assigned in the order that they are received in the first-available method; whereas, in the best method, no frequency assignments are made until all requirements are known. Then the requirements are re-ordered so that the most difficult requirements (those with the most incompatibilities) are assigned first. In a practical application, the best method can only be used in a new service, or when a band is completely repacked. However, it might be possible to assign frequencies to blocks of requirements rather than one-at-a-time. The advantage of this strategy is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Spectrum cost of small block assignments

Block size	bandwidth % increase
100	0.0
50	6.2
20	12.1
10	14.3
1	21.2

Table 2 shows that assigning frequencies as requirements are received takes more than 20 % more total bandwidth than assigning all 100 requirements at once. If requirements are held until 20 can be assigned with one run of the computer program, about 40 % of the extra bandwidth can be saved.

A final example will show how the program can be used to study scenarios with complex frequency-distance separation rules and actual (rather than random) transmitter locations. In this example, the benefits of relaxing the UHF taboos is examined. The "UHF taboos" are an extensive set of frequency-distance separation rules developed to protect simple, early UHF television receivers. They are shown in Table 3 [13].

Table 3. UHF Television taboos

Channel sep	Distance sep, mi
0	155
1	55
2	20
3	20
4	20
5	20
7	60
8	20
14	60
15	75

Receiver technology has improved in the thirty-odd years since these rules were developed, and the prospect of high-definition TV, which requires more bandwidth, motivated a determination of the spectrum cost of the taboos. A realistic set of transmitter locations was obtained by selecting all licensed UHF transmitters in the eastern half of the contiguous United States. The frequency assignment computer program was used to find the minimum number of channels required to assign all these stations under the taboos, and various arbitrary relaxations of the taboos. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Number of channels needed to assign eastern US UHF-TV transmitters

F-D rules	no. ch.	%
Taboos	47	100
0.75 x T	41	87
0.50 x T	34	72
0.25 x T	32	68
0.00 x T	32	68

The co-channel and adjacent-channel separation distances were those in Table 3 for all sets of F-D rules. The notation "NxT" in Table 4 means that all separation distances except for the co-channel and adjacent-channel separation distances were multiplied by N. The successive lines in

Table 4 show the effects of decreasing these other separation distances. Eliminating all but the co-channel and adjacent channel separation rules reduces the amount of spectrum needed by 32 %.

USING OPTIMUM FREQUENCY SELECTION IN THE TWENTY-FIRST CENTURY

The preceding examples show that the methodology exists for increasing the number of systems that can operate in a service band while maintaining the required signal-to-interference ratio. The computer program described can compute the optimum allotment table for any set of requirements--taken as a whole, as blocks, or one-at-a-time. But the program is not being used by the spectrum management authorities (NTIA and FCC) because the current administrative procedures do not provide for it. The benefits of optimum frequency selection technology will be realized only if these procedures are changed.

The first change needed is to allow the spectrum management authorities to select the specific frequency to be assigned to a requirement. The prospective user's application would state the communication requirements of the system--its location, coverage area, traffic load, etc., and the service band that is appropriate. The spectrum management authority would then use the computer program to select the specific frequency that would meet those requirements within the agreed upon protection ratios while minimizing the spectrum used by all systems in the band.

As shown by table 2, the best results would be obtained if the frequencies were assigned to blocks of requirements. Thus, users should be encouraged to apply for frequencies as far in advance of their requirement as possible, so that the assigning authority could collect blocks of requirements to be assigned in one computer run.

CONCLUSIONS

The technology exists to use radio service bands efficiently by correctly choosing the specific frequency assigned to each requirement so that the group of all requirements uses the minimum total bandwidth. Present administrative procedures do not provide for the use of the technology. Changing the administrative procedures would result in more efficient use of the spectrum.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. A. Zoellner, "Frequency assignment games and strategies," IEEE Trans. on Electromagn. Compat., vol EMC-15, pp. 191-196, Nov. 1973.
- [2] J. A. Zoellner and C. L. Beall, "A breakthrough in spectrum conserving frequency assignment technology," IEEE Trans. Electromagn. Compat., vol. EMC-19, pp. 313-319, Aug. 1977.
- [3] W. K. Hale, "Frequency Assignment: Theory and Applications," Proc. IEEE, vol. 68, pp. 1497-1514, Dec. 1980.
- [4] W. K. Hale, "New spectrum management tools, Proc. of 1981 IEEE Int. Symp. on EMC, pp. 47-53, 1981.
- [5] L. A. Berry and D. H. Cronin, "The spectrum cost of frequency-distance separation rules," Proc. of 1983 Int. Symp. on EMC, pp. 75-78, 1983.
- [6] L. A. Berry and D. H. Cronin, "Spectrum-efficient frequency assignment in mixed service bands," Proc. 1982 IEEE Int. Symp. EMC, pp. 7-10, 1982.
- [7] D. H. Cronin and L. A. Berry, "The effect of bandwidth and interference rejection on the spectrum efficiency of land mobile radio systems," NTIA Report 83-139, 1983.
- [8] J. S. Washburn, L. A. Berry, and C. M. Rush, "The HF Broadcasting Model: A comparison of two versions," NTIA Report 87-217, 1987.
- [9] International Telecommunications Union, "World Administrative Radio Conference for the Planning of the HF Band Allocated to the Broadcasting Service, Geneva, 1984, Report to the Second Session of the Conference," General Secretariat of the ITU, Geneva.
- [10] International Frequency Registration Board, "HFBC Planning System," 1986, ITU, Geneva.
- [11] Federal Communication Commission, "Report of the Spectrum Utilization and Alternatives Working Party of the Planning Subcommittee of the Advisory Committee on Advanced Television Service," FCC, 1988.
- [12] R. Eckert, A. Stillwell, and B. Franca, "Interim Report: Further Studies of the Availability of Spectrum for Advanced Television," OET Technical Memorandum FCC/OET TM89-1, FCC, 1989.
- [13] Code of Federal Regulations, Parts 73.610 and 73.699, 1987.